

Amperometric Determination of Thiocyanate, Thiosulphate and Hydrogen Peroxide with Manganese(III) Pyrophosphate*

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Microquantities of thiocyanate, thiosulphate and hydrogen peroxide have been successfully determined amperometrically with manganese(III) pyrophosphate using rotating platinum micro electrode as an indicator electrode and saturated calomel electrode as reference at 0.00V in 2M phosphoric acid. A fairly large amount of Cl^- , F^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- and ClO_4^- do not interfere.

THE stability of manganese(III) solutions increase in presence of the complexing reagents. Manganese(III) in the form of pyrophosphate is more stable than that of sulphate. The use of manganese(III) compounds in titrametric analysis has been reviewed¹. Potentiometric² and spectrophotometric³ methods of end point detection have been adopted in some of the reactions studied so far. Recently we have studied the ion exchange behaviour of manganese(III) pyrophosphate⁴ and have used it as an amperometric titrant^{5,6} for determination of complex organic and inorganic materials. In the present communication we show its use for the determination of thiocyanate, thiosulphate and hydrogen peroxide.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of A. R. (BDH) or extrapure E. Merck quality. The solutions of thiocyanate, thiosulphate and hydrogen peroxide were prepared in double distilled water and standardised by conventional titrametric methods. Manganese(III) pyrophosphate was prepared by the method suggested by Belcher and West⁷ and standardised with standard arsenic(III) solution.

Manganese(III) pyrophosphate polarograms in 1.5-2.5M phosphoric acid showed that manganese is reduced from trivalent to divalent state at positive potentials. A potential of 0.00 V vs SCE corresponding to the diffusion current plateau of manganese(III) pyrophosphate was chosen for the amperometric study. Current measurements were made with Toshniwal (India) manual polarograph using rotating platinum micro electrode (1800 rpm) as indicator electrode.

Procedure :

Titrations carried out over a wide range of phosphoric acid concentration showed that reproducible and accurate results were obtained over a concentration range of 1.5-2.5 M.

In the actual oxidimetric procedure requisite quantity of phosphoric acid was added to an aliquot of reducing material to be determined so as to maintain the overall concentration at 2 M. A potential of 0.00V vs SCE was applied. After each addition of an aliquot of manganese(III) pyrophosphate, the galvanometer reading was noted. The readings corrected for volume change were plotted against the titrant volume. The diffusion current was constant up to the equivalence point and increased afterwards giving reversed L shaped curve. The end point was located graphically as the point of intersection of two straight lines. Reverse titration was followed for the determination of thiosulphate.

Results and Discussion

The methods of estimation of thiocyanate, thiosulphate and hydrogen peroxide depend on the following reactions⁸⁻¹⁰

The results in Table 1 shows that microquantities of thiocyanate, thiosulphate and hydrogen peroxide can be determined accurately using managanimetric amperometric technique.

The reverse titration was found to be suitable for the determination of thiosulphate because of the slow decomposition and possible formation of sulphur in phosphoric acid.

Study of the effect of Diverse ions :

The effect of diverse ions was studied by taking requisite amount of thiocyanate (0.245 mg), thiosulphate (1.25 mg) and hydrogen peroxide (0.066 mg)

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TABLE 1—AMPEROMETRIC DETERMINATION OF THIOCYANATE, THIOSULPHATE AND HYDROGEN PEROXIDE WITH MANGANESE(III) PYROPHOSPHATE AT 0.00V vs SOE WITH ROTATING PLATINUM ELECTRODE IN 2M PHOSPHORIC ACID

Amount present, mg	Amount found, mg	% Error
SCN⁻		
0.1835	0.1835	—
0.3058	0.3076	+0.58
0.3669	0.3670	+0.02
0.4281	0.4290	+0.21
0.4892	0.4884	-0.16
S₂O₈²⁻		
0.4168	0.4196	+0.68
0.8936	0.8918	-0.21
1.0420	1.0490	+0.16
1.2540	1.2590	+0.39
1.4590	1.4530	-0.41
H₂O₂		
0.0937	0.0938	-1.18
0.0506	0.0506	—
0.0664	0.0664	—
0.0843	0.0898	-0.59
0.1012	0.1011	-0.09

and adding different amounts of diverse ions. The ions Br⁻, I⁻ and CN⁻ even present in small amounts interfere seriously. A fairly large amounts of Cl⁻ (53 mg), F⁻ (28 mg), SO₄²⁻ (37 mg), NO₃⁻ (40 mg),

ClO₄⁻ (70 mg) and CH₃COO⁻ (125 mg) do not interfere.

Since manganese(III) pyrophosphate is reduced at positive potentials deaeration of the solutions is not necessary. Furthermore amperometric method is more rapid and simple, where the equivalence point can be determined from few readings before and after the end point.

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